

Counting Return and Understanding Transition: Syrian Refugee and IDP Movements

Sefa Secen

Sefa Secen is an Assistant Professor of Political Science and Director of the International and Global Studies Program at Nazareth University in Rochester, NY. Before joining Nazareth, he was a Postdoctoral Fellow at the Mershon Center for International Security Studies at Ohio State University. He earned his PhD in Political Science from the Maxwell School of Syracuse University. He studies international relations theory, migration, and political behavior with a regional focus on the Middle East. His scholarship has appeared in leading academic journals and major media outlets, including the Journal of Global Security Studies, Politics, Groups, and Identities, European Politics and Society, Turkish Studies, Forced Migration Review, Oxford Research Encyclopedia of International Studies, Migration and Development, TIME, The Washington Post, and The Conversation.

In the aftermath of more than a decade of conflict, the question of return looms large in Syria's future. "Refugee return" is often invoked as a marker of stability and a step toward national recovery. Yet the reality is far more complicated. Returns are partial, often temporary, and deeply entangled with the processes of post-conflict reconstruction. They are rarely a linear "end state" but part of a dynamic mobility cycle that can include multiple departures before settlement becomes sustainable. Moreover, how we count returns and what those numbers reveal or conceal are very important.

Despite the appearance of a more settled political map, Syria still remains a country in motion. Refugees cross borders back into Syria, sometimes only to leave again; internally displaced persons (IDPs) shuttle between camps, informal settlements, and damaged home communities; and local flare-ups of violence continue to disrupt return plans. These movements resist the linear narrative of "going home" and instead reflect a churn of return and remigration that will likely define Syria's "transition" for years to come. Studies on circular and stepwise migration show that returns are likely to be followed by remigra-

tion, and such patterns are neither unique to Syria nor inherently short-lived—they often reflect deliberate household strategies to manage risk (de Haas, 2010; Sahin-Mencutek, 2023). In the Syrian case, these "test returns" and staggered movements are a rational adaptation to volatile conditions. The politics of return are, therefore, inseparable from the politics of transition. How return is measured, represented, and acted upon can also shape not just humanitarian planning but also Syria's contested postwar order.

The Measurement Challenge

Measuring return migration is never straightforward, even in peacetime. As Oliver Bakewell (1999) and Richard Black (2002) argue, migration statistics are socially and politically constructed; they reflect not only movements but also the bureaucratic and political systems that record them. In recent years, datafication has become a core feature of migration governance. Despite the contentious negotiations over the Global Compact for Migration (GCM) in 2017–2018, the quantification of migration through digital technologies garnered widespread support from states, many of which have built digi-

tized systems of data collection, analysis, and dissemination. Yet states' reporting rarely aligns. In the 1970s, for example, German data on Italian repatriation exceeded Italy's own statistics on return from Germany by a factor of two, as Russell King (1993) notes. In Poland in the 1990s, substantial returns went uncounted because many emigrants in the 1980s had never registered as emigrants (Koser, 2016). These cases underscore a broader point: definitions of "return migration" and the methods used to count it vary widely—even within a single country, sometimes across different agencies (de Haas, Castles, & Miller, 2020).

Syria exemplifies these challenges. Some refugees re-enter without passing through official crossing points or notifying host-country authorities; others undertake short-term or circular returns that may not be captured at all. The result is a statistical picture that is necessarily incomplete. A further conceptual distinction is critical: flows versus stocks. Flow data captures how many people return over a specific period (weekly, monthly, annually), while stock data reflects the total size of the returned population at a point in time. Flows reveal short-term dynamics and policy effects; stocks indicate the cumulative scale of reintegration challenges. Conflating the two risks obscuring the patterns that matter most for understanding the evolving return landscape in a given context. As I discuss in the following paragraphs, the UN Refugee Agency (UNHCR)'s governorate-level data on Syrian refugee returns demonstrate why this distinction matters. Short-term dips in flows often track local fighting, while gradual increases in stocks signal more sustained—if still fragile—settlement.

What the Numbers Tell Us

While return numbers are always contested, UNHCR provides the most systematic and widely used data available. According to its Operational Data Portal, between 2016 and October 2024, approximately 435,395 Syrian refugees were recorded as having returned to the country, most to opposition-controlled areas. After the fall of the Assad regime, recorded returns surged, with UNHCR reporting 746,360 people—a sharp increase in a relatively short period. Figure 1 visualizes the return statistics across Syria's fourteen governorates after the fall of the regime, between 8 December 2024 and 31 July 2025, and Figure 2 provides the overall return statistics since 2016. Figure 1 reveals the uneven geography of these returns.

Densely populated areas and regions such as Aleppo, Damascus, Idlib, and Rural Damascus account for the largest shares, with Aleppo alone recording over 145,499 returns. Aleppo's high figures may also reflect its role as one of the main origins of Syrian refugees, particularly to Turkey, which hosts the largest number of Syrians overall. By contrast, smaller or more contested governorates such as as-Sweida, Quneitra, and Tartous saw far fewer returns. Ar-Raqqa is also an outlier: cumulative totals declined between December and July, reflecting net out-migration/secondary displacement and possible revisions to enumerations rather than steady inflows. These patterns are consistent with Raqqa's recent history of control, which has shaped both demographic change and return intentions. The city fell to opposition forces in early March 2013; ISIS then consolidated control and declared Raqqa its de facto capital in 2014; and the predominantly Kurdish Syrian Democratic Forces recaptured the city in October 2017.

Figure 1. Syrian Refugee Returns between December 8, 2024, and July 31, 2025.
Source: UNHCR, 2025 (Syria Governorates of Return Overview)

Figure 2. All Syrian Refugee Returns between 2016 and July 31, 2025
Source: UNHCR, 2025 (Syria Governorates of Return Overview)

Temporal analysis sheds further light on these dynamics. Figure 3 shows that while Aleppo and Damascus saw steady, sustained growth in return numbers, other governorates experienced more irregular trajectories, with sudden surges followed by stagnation or decline. Ar-Raqqa's early-2025 downturn indicates how quickly return gains can reverse.

The internal displacement picture is equally significant. As of July 2025, approximately 7.4 million people remain displaced within Syria's borders. Of these, 5.1 million live outside formal IDP sites, while 1.35 million reside in 1,671 camps and collective shelters across northwest and northeast Syria. Since 27 November 2024, more than 1.58 million IDPs

Figure 3. Monthly Cumulative Returns by Governorate
Source: UNHCR, 2025 (Syria Governorates of Return Overview)

For Syrian refugees, UNHCR's own intention surveys show that decisions to return are shaped by a combination of “push” factors in host countries—such as rising hostility, economic crisis, or deportation risk—and “pull” factors in Syria, including family reunification, property claims, and perceived improvements in security. Yet, as research by Kayaoglu, Sahin-Mencutek, and Erdogan (2021) and Alrababah et al. (2023) demonstrates, these “pull” factors, especially perceived safety, often remain critical but can shift rapidly. In the Syrian context, governorate-level return data confirm that security, economic opportunity, and governance quality vary so widely across the country that the calculus of return is fundamentally localized.

have returned to their areas of origin, including 774,788 who left IDP sites after 8 December 2024 (UNHCR IDP Return Overview, 2025).

Return as a Mirror of Transition

Why do these patterns matter for understanding Syria's transition? On the political front, the Asad regime's fall has increased the return numbers and intentions but has not yet translated into mass voluntary return. Economically, Syria remains in deep crisis. Infrastructure destruction and lack of basic services in many localities mean that even those willing to risk return might face formidable barriers to reintegration. In some cases,

return is also less a choice than the end point of deteriorating conditions in host states. Lebanon’s economic implosion, Turkey’s political polarization around refugee policy, and Jordan’s recalibrated approach all illustrate how host-country dynamics can also drive return patterns, although not as much as conditions inside Syria.

As Figure 4 shows, of the 746,360 people who returned between 8 December 2024 and 31 July 2025, roughly 41% originated from Lebanon ($\approx 306,760$), 36% from Turkey ($\approx 268,689$), 16% from Jordan ($\approx 119,418$), and about 7% from Iraq and Egypt combined ($\approx 55,230$), with a small remainder from other countries. Interpreted relative to refugee populations in these host countries, indicative return rates are highest in Lebanon (on the order of $\sim 30\%$), followed by Jordan ($\sim 20\%$) and Turkey ($\sim 10\%$). Returns from Europe remain negligible by comparison; for instance, only about 1,337 Syrians out of roughly 973,000 have returned from Germany after the fall of Asad (DW, 2025). These cross-country differences also demonstrate that host-states’ polit-

ical, economic, and asylum policies shape “voluntary” return. Beyond general conditions, whether protection is temporary or permanent—and whether there are pathways to longer-term residence or citizenship—plays a decisive role in refugees’ calculus to remain abroad or to return despite continuing challenges in the country of origin.

Finally, tracking not only the how many but the how and why of return is key to understanding whether Syria’s “transition” is moving toward stability or simply entering another cycle of conflict. In the end, counting returns is more than a statistical exercise. It is a means of taking the pulse of a society in flux. The patterns of who goes back, under what conditions, and with what prospects for staying offer an unvarnished view of the realities behind the headlines. In Syria, as in other post-conflict contexts, the politics of return will remain central to the politics of transition itself. ♦

Figure 4. Return by the Host Country since December 8
Source: UNHCR, 2025 (Syria Governorates of Return Overview)

References

- Alrababah, Ala', Daniel Masterson, Marine Casalis, Dominik Hangartner, and Jeremy Weinstein. 2023. "The Dynamics of Refugee Return: Syrian Refugees and Their Migration Intentions." *British Journal of Political Science* 53 (4): 1108–1131.
- Bakewell, Oliver. 1999. "Can We Ever Rely on Refugee Statistics?" *Radical Statistics* 72 (1).
- Black, Richard, and Saskia Gent. 2006. "Sustainable Return in Post-Conflict Contexts." *International Migration* 44 (1): 15–38.
- Black, Richard, and Khalid Koser, eds. 1999. *The End of the Refugee Cycle? Refugee Repatriation and Reconstruction. Forced Migration* Vol. 4. New York: Berghahn Books.
- De Haas, Hein. 2010. *Migration Transitions: A Theoretical and Empirical Inquiry into the Developmental Drivers of International Migration*. International Migration Institute Working Paper 24. University of Oxford.
- De Haas, Hein, Stephen Castles, and Mark J. Miller. 2020. *The Age of Migration: International Population Movements in the Modern World*. 6th ed. New York: Guilford Press.
- Deutsche Welle. 2025. "Germany: 1,300 Syrians Return Home Since Fall of Assad." DW, August 13.
- Kayaoglu, Ahmet, Zeynep Şahin-Mencütek, and M. Murat Erdoğan. 2021. "Return Aspirations of Syrian Refugees in Turkey." *Journal of Immigrant & Refugee Studies* 20 (4): 561–583.
- King, Russell. 1993. "Recent Immigration to Italy: Character, Causes and Consequences." *GeoJournal* 30: 283–292.
- Koser, Khalid. 2016. *International Migration: A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR). n.d. "Global Compact for Migration."
- Şahin-Mencütek, Zeynep. 2023. *The Role of Return Preparedness, Assistance and Networks in Returnees' Reintegration in Origin Countries (Synthesis Report)*. Bonn: Bonn International Center for Conversion (BICC).
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). 2025. Operational Data Portal.
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). 2025. Syria Governorates IDPs and IDP Returnees Overview.
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). 2025. Syria Governorates of Return Overview.